

ERSIN DEMIREL

Cicadidae (Hemiptera: Auchenorrhyncha) from Mt. Musa, Turkey

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Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Tayfur Sökmen Campus, Faculty Sciences and Arts, Biology Department,
31060 Antakya/Hatay/Turkey,
auchenorrhyncha@mku.edu.tr

Abstract: In this study, the Cicadidae from Mt Musa (Hatay Province, Turkey) are recorded from an evaluation of 33 specimens. The following six species are identified: *Cicada lodosi* BOULARD, 1979, *Cicada mordoganensis* BOULARD, 1979, *Cicadatra platyptera* FIEBER, 1876, *Oligoglena turcica* (SCHEDL, 2001), *Oligoglena tibialis* (PANZER, 1798) and *Pagiphora annulata* (BRULLÉ, 1832). Among these, only *Pagiphora annulata* (BRULLÉ, 1832) has previously been recorded from Hatay Province, the others are new local records for Mt. Musa and Hatay. Distributional information of all species is updated and shown on a map of Turkey and elsewhere. Also important morphological characters of the species were photographed. Resulting from this work, the number of known species from the region is increased from one to six.

Key words: *Cicada*, *Cicadatra*, *Oligoglena*, *Pagiphora*, Hatay, Turkey, Zoogeography, Endemism.

Introduction

Cicadas are large and loud singing insects which can reach from 1 cm to 10 cm. They have a broad head, large compound eyes, and long, usually transparent wings. Their songs vary from species to species through differences in the resonating chamber (BRAMBILA & HODGES 2008).

Although the superfamily Cicadoidea WESTWOOD, 1840 includes, four subfamilies, 41 tribes, 428 genera, and almost 2900 described species (almost all of them are Cicadidae) (BARTLETT *et al.* 2018), it is thought to be composed of 4000 species (BRAMBILA & HODGES 2008). Although six families have been recognised, recent studies suggest only two families are present, the small Tettigarctidae (from Australia) and the Cicadidae. According to structure of the male genitalia, wing venation, tymbal covers, and opercula characteristics, the species of Cicadidae are separated to three subfamilies (SANBORN 2008).

Cicadas spread from the tundra to the tropics. Both adults and nymphs are polyphagous. Nymphs are subterranean and feed on perennial roots. They are facultatively endothermic

because they can warm themselves through shivering with flight and/or tymbal muscles or cool themselves by releasing water (i.e., evaporative cooling) (BRAMBILA & HODGES 2008).

Cicadoidea comprises more than 3000 described species world-wide (SANBORN 2014) of which Cicadidae is represented by 168 species in the Palaearctic (NAST 1972) including 32 species from Turkey, some endemic (NAST 1972, LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KOÇAK & KEMAL 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011).

Generally, the vast majority of work on the Turkish cicada fauna is based on short touristic trips by foreign researchers. Studies by Turkish researchers is in the form of either an assessment of all families of the suborder Auchenorrhyncha except Cicadoidea. When the literature is investigated, it is found that Cicadidae is represented by 32 species in Turkey and it seems that only *Pagiphora annulata* (BRULLÉ, 1832) is recorded from Hatay province.

The first records of Cicadidae from Turkey were given by foreign researchers (FIEBER (1872, 1876), METCALF (1963), OSHANIN (1908, 1912), FAHRINGER (1922), BODENHEIMER (1958), DLABOLA (1957, 1971a, 1971b), LINNAVUORI (1965), NAST (1972) and BOULARD (1979, 1993)) being the main examples of these researchers. Leading Turkish researchers include Ayla Kalkandelen, Niyazi Lodos and Emine Demir. In addition, Veysel Kartal made a postdoctoral study on this group in 1979. However, the vast majority of other works on Auchenorrhyncha are not directly related to Cicadidae including my own PhD thesis called „Auchenorrhyncha’s (Hemiptera) of Bolkar Mountains”.

Mt. Musa is located to the south of the Amanos Mountains, which is located in Hatay province and the Mediterranean Phytogeographical region. It is surrounded by the Mediterranean Sea in the west, the Samandağ District in the south, Gömbece Stream in the east and the Amanos Mountains in the north. Altitude varies between 0-1281 m. Since there are more slopes in the north and north-western part of the mountain, the altitude suddenly rises to 350 m and therefore, it is more difficult to access the inner parts of the mountain from here.

On the south and southeast sides, the slope is relatively little and because of this there are many settlements (Kaburluk, Çevlik, Mağaracık, Vakıflı, Kapısuğu, Yoğunluk, Hıdırbey, Eriklikuyu, Teknepınarı, İkizköprü, Çamlıyayla) (DÜZENLİ & ÇAKAN 2001) and here there are traces of „upper cretaceous”, „lower paleozoic” and „quaternary” geological time periods in the rock structure (YILMAZ *et al.* 1984).

The region is under the influence of typical Mediterranean climate. According to the data that obtained from Samandağ meteorological station, the amount of annual rainfall is 997 mm. Snow is rarely seen in December and March. The average annual temperature is 18.8° C. Precipitation is effective in the deep valleys of the north and northeast, but less in the south. Rainfall regime is winter, spring, autumn and summer (DÜZENLİ & ÇAKAN 2001). As a result of climate, the region is dominated by shrubs and forest vegetation.

The purpose of this study is to record the Cicadidae fauna of Mt. Musa, expanding the distribution of species previously known from Turkey, determining whether previously recorded species still exist and last but not least, providing comparative material for future studies by Turkish and foreign researchers.

Material and Methods

This study is based on 27 male and 6 female Cicadidae collected by sweep net from 10 different localities on Mt. Musa during the months of June to September of 2013-2014 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Study area.

Samples were killed in a jar containing ethyl acetate vapor and protected by enveloping. Morphological characteristics were preliminarily applied for identification of the specimens and male genitalia parts were extracted according to OSSIANNILSSON 1970 for definite diagnosis.

All the investigation and photograph studies were made with Nikon SMZ745T trinocular zoom stereomicroscope.

The distributional maps of each species at the Mt. Musa were created with Arcview 3.3 software by using the coordinates which has been taken from the Garmin Monterra GPS (Global Positioning System).

While evaluating the samples, DEMIR 1998, 2005, 2006, 2007a, 2007b, 2008, DEMIREL 2010, DMITRIEV 2017, EMELJANOV 1964, KARTAL 1983, 1988, 1999, 2006, KARTAL & ZEYBEKOGLU 1999a, 1999b, MELICHAR 1896, HOLZINGER *et al.* 2003, PUISSANT 2002, REMANE & WACHMANN 1993 and SCHEDL 1999 have been used.

The general and local distribution of the species are given from NAST 1972, 1982, 1987, LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010 and the other individual papers.

Identified species are given below in alphabetical order.

Results

A key to the species of Cicadidae from Hatay province.

1. Body length greater than 25 mm except wing 2
 - Body length not more than 25 mm except wing 3
2. First femoral spur of the front leg thin and tip of spur pointed (Fig. 8b) *Cicada lodosi*
 - First femoral spur of the front leg more or less triangular and tip of spur rounded (Fig. 10b) *Cicada mordoganensis*
3. A vein of the radial cell of fore wing seems like a spoon (Fig. 14a) *Pagiphora annulata*
 - A vein of the radial cell of fore wing not seems like a spoon 4
4. M+R and Cu veins fused at the corner of basal cell 5
 - M+R and Cu veins distinctly separated at the corner of basal cell (Fig. 11a) *Cicadatra platyptera*
5. Hind wings with 5 apical cell (Fig. 12a) *Oligoglena turcica*
 - Hind wings with 6 apical cell (Fig. 13a) *Oligoglena tibialis*

Cicada lodosi BOULARD, 1979

(Figs. 2, 8)

Material examined. 1♀, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province, 36°11'27"N, 35°53'50"E, 239m, 8 VIII 2013, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 2c).

Distribution.

Palearctic: Endemic for Turkey (NAST 1982) (Fig. 2a).

Turkey: Antalya, İzmir and Manisa (BOULARD 1979, LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011). This species is new record for Hatay Province (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2. a–c. *Cicada lodosi* BOULARD, 1979, distributions: a – Palearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Cicada mordoganensis BOULARD, 1979

(Figs. 3, 9, 10)

Material examined. 2♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province, 36°11'7"N, 35°54'21"E, 360 m, 8 VIII 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 3♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province, 36°11'27"N, 35°53'50"E, 239 m, 8 VIII 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 2♀♀, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Kaburluk Province, 36°10'59"N, 35°52'59"E, 20 m, 21 VIII 2013, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 3c).

Distribution.

Palaearctic: Endemic for Turkey (NAST 1982) (Fig. 3a).

Turkey: Antalya, İzmir and Muğla (BOULARD 1979, LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011) (Fig. 3b). This species is new record for Hatay Province.

Fig. 3. a–c. *Cicada mordoganensis* BOULARD, 1979, distributions: a – Palaearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Cicadatra platyptera FIEBER, 1876

(Figs. 4, 11)

Material examined. 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu, 36°8'40"N, 35°59'28"E, 290 m, 18 VII 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çamlıyayla, 36°10'34"N, 35°58'41"E, 768 m, 18 VII 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 3♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu, 36°8'59"N, 35°59'45"E, 286 m, 31 VII 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 1♀, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu, 36°8'40"N, 35°59'28"E, 290 m, 8 VIII 2013, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 4c).

Distribution.

Palaearctic: Israel, Iran, Jordan, Lebanon, Russia, Syria and Turkey (NAST 1972) (Fig. 4a).

Turkey: Giresun, Gümüşhane, İzmir, Konya, Muğla and Sivas (LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011) (Fig. 4b). This species is new record for Hatay Province.

Fig. 4. a–c. *Cicadatra platyptera* FIEBER, 1876, distributions: a – Palaearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Oligoglana turcica (SCHEDL, 2001)

(Figs. 5, 12)

Material examined. 2♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu, 36°8'34"N, 35°54'32"E, 30 V 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Hıdırbey Village (Cruise Terrace), 36°8'3"N, 35°58'32"E, 243 m, 13 VI 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 5♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu Village, 36°8'39"N, 35°59'27"E, 284 m, 13 VI 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Kapısuu Cemetery, 36°7'58"N, 35°57'8"E, 372 m, 27 VI 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 4♂♂, 1♀, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Eriklikuyu, 36°8'40"N, 35°59'28"E, 290 m, 27 VI 2013, leg. E. Demirel; 2♂♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Yoğunuluk Province, 36°08'39"N, 35°59'27"E, 285 m, 20 V 2016, leg. E. Demirel; 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province, 36°11'03"N, 35°52'55"E, 73 m, 28 VI 2016, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 5c).

Distribution.

Palaearctic: Endemic for Turkey (Fig. 5a).

Turkey: Gaziantep and Kahramanmaraş (LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, SCHEDL 2001, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011) (Fig. 5b). This species is new record for Hatay Province.

Fig. 5. a–c. *Oligoglena turcica* (SCHEDL, 2001), distributions: a – Palearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Fig. 6. a–c. *Oligoglena tibialis* (PANZER, 1798), distributions: a – Palearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Oligoglena tibialis (PANZER, 1798)

(Figs. 6, 13)

Material examined. 1♀, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province, 36°11'2"N, 35°52'58"E, 76 m, 13 VI 2013, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 6c).

Distribution.

Palearctic: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czechia, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Morocco, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine and Uzbekistan (NAST 1972, 1987) (Fig. 6a).

Turkey: Adana, Ankara, Artvin, Çorum and İzmir (LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011, MOL 2017) (Fig. 6b). This species is new record for Hatay Province.

Pagiphora annulata (BRULLÉ)

(Figs. 7, 14)

Material examined. 1♂, Turkey, East Mediterranean, Hatay, Samandağ, Çevlik, Kaburluk Province (Old Garrison), 36°11'9"N, 35°53'8"E, 102 m, 18 VII 2013, leg. E. Demirel (Fig. 7c).

Distribution.

Palearctic: Albania, Algeria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Kosovo, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia and Turkey (NAST 1972, 1987) (Fig. 7a).

Turkey: Çanakkale, Hatay, İçel, İzmir, Tekirdağ and Zonguldak (LODOS & KALKANDELEN 1981, 1988, KEMAL & KOÇAK 2010, ÖNDER *et al.* 2011) (Fig. 7b).

Fig. 7. a–c. *Pagiphora annulata* (BRULLÉ, 1832), distributions: a – Palearctic; b – Turkey; c – Hatay Province.

Discussion

In this study, six Cicadidae from Hatay Province were identified, i.e., *Cicada lodosi* (Fig. 8.), *Cicada mordoganensis* (Figs. 9–10), *Cicadatra platyptera* (Fig. 11), *Oligoglana turcica* (Fig. 12), *Oligoglana tibialis* (Fig. 13) and *Pagiphora annulata* (Fig. 14).

Fig. 8. a–c. *Cicada lodosi* BOULARD, 1979, female: a – habitus dorsal view; b – femoral spurs; c – genital plate and ovipositor ventral view.

Cicada lodosi, *Cicada mordoganensis*, *Cicadatra platyptera*, *Oligoglana turcica* and *Oligoglana tibialis* were previously recorded from Turkey but are newly recorded here from Hatay province. Also, *Pagiphora annulata* (Brullé, 1832) is recorded for the second time from the study area.

Oligoglana turcica was described by Schedl (2001) from only 7 specimens (3♂♂, 4♀♀) collected from Gaziantep and Kahramanmaraş provinces. In this study, 17 specimens (16♂♂, 1♀) were collected constituting more than half of the previously collected specimens.

Cicada lodosi, *Cicada mordoganensis* and *Oligoglana turcica* remain endemic for Turkey but it is possible that these species can also be found in neighboring countries such as Syria, Iraq, Iran and Jordan.

With this study, the number of known species from Hatay was increased to six by adding 5 new records. It is thought that this number may increase even more with the work to be done in a wider area.

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Fig. 9. a–g. *Cicada mordoganensis* BOULARD, 1979, male: a – habitus dorsal view; b – anal tube outside view; c – pygophore lateral view; d – anal tube lateral view; e – aedeagus lateral view; f – VII. abdominal sternum ventral view; g – VIII. abdominal sternum ventral view.

Fig. 10. a–c. *Cicada mordoganensis* BOULARD, 1979, female: a – habitus dorsal view; b – femoral spurs; c – genital plate and ovipositor ventral view.

Fig. 11. a–g. *Cicadatra platyptera* FIEBER, 1876, male: a – habitus dorsal view; female: b – genital plate and ovipositor ventral view; c – pygophore lateral view; d – anal tube outside view; e – aedeagus lateral view; f – VII. abdominal sternum ventral view; g – VIII. abdominal sternum ventral view.

Fig. 12. a-f. *Oligoglana turcica* (SCHEDL, 2001) male: a – habitus dorsal view; female: b – genital plate and ovipositor ventral view; c – pygophore lateral view; d – anal tube outside view; e – aedeagus lateral view; f – VIII. abdominal sternum ventral view.

Fig. 13. *Oligoglana tibialis* (PANZER, 1798), female: a – habitus dorsal view; b – genital plate and ovipositor ventral view.

Fig. 14. a–f. *Pagiphora annulata* (BRULLÉ, 1832) male: a – habitus dorsal view; b – pygophore lateral view; c – anal tube outside view; d – aedeagus lateral view; e – VII. abdominal sternum ventral view; f – VIII. abdominal sternum ventral view.

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